

JUNE 20-22, 2019, OPLENAC, TOPOLA, SERBIA

THIRD JOINT MEETING OF NATIONAL PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

In the organisation of a

SLOVAK AND SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETIES

**HEALTH RISK,
NUTRITION AND DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS:
OXIDATIVE STRESS AND POLYPHENOLS IN
THE HEART OF SERBIAN WINERIES**

*OPLENAC
TOPOLA
2019*

FINAL PROGRAM & ABSTRACT BOOK

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SLOVAK PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETY
SERBIAN PHYSIOLOGICAL SOCIETY

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<http://www.physiology.org.rs/3thNPS/>

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VASCULAR DYSFUNCTION FOLLOWING BREATH-HOLD DIVING

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The pathogenesis of predominantly neurological decompression sickness (DCS) in breath-hold diving is probably multifactorial and cannot be explained only by arterialized venous gas emboli. In SCUBA diving other areas have been investigated with links to DCS including microparticles, impairment of endothelial function and platelet activation, suggesting complex mechanisms. This study focused on the vascular damage and how it fits into the puzzle of DCS genesis in breath-hold diving. Eleven breath-hold divers participated in a field study and completed two different diving protocols separated by two days without diving. Protocol 1 consisted of five deep dives with short surface periods, protocol 2 of repetitive dives lasting for six hours. Endothelium-dependent vasodilator function of the brachial artery was assessed pre- and post-dive using the flow-mediated dilation (FMD) approach. All FMD measures were analysed by two-way within-subject analysis of variance (ANOVA; factors: time – pre-/post-dive, protocol – deep/repetitive dive). Absolute FMD was reduced following both diving protocols ($p < 0.001$). There was no interaction ($p = 0.288$) and main effect of protocol ($p = 0.151$). The same main effect of time persisted following allometric scaling for baseline diameter and including shear rate area under the curve (SRAUC) and baseline diameters as covariates. The SRAUC stimulus remained the same in all measuring conditions ($p = 0.529$). Both deep and repetitive breath-hold diving leads to endothelial dysfunction that may play an important role in the genesis of DCS.